

An Inclusive Ethical Framework for Research with People with Diverse Disabilities

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People in power and position mainly frame research ethics. But do they include the voices of people with diverse disabilities? Do they value human over selfish intentions? People with disabilities are not objects, and they should not be misused. It is essential to recognize that not all disabilities are the same, nor are all contexts identical. Researchers often lack this contextual understanding. While they may have experience, they often lack exposure to diverse realities.

Fragility and vulnerability are powerful, so why treat them as objects for personal or professional gain? Why not frame research design with them as co-creators of knowledge? This proposed framework is designed for researchers who desire to work with people with diverse disabilities.

Inclusive Ethical Framework		
Disability and Inclusive Language Capacity Building; Field Visit	Exploring Inherent Human Biases through Identity Exploration	Respecting Wellbeing and Autonomy; Avoid Exploitation
Ethical Approval from the Institute with Inclusive Members	Participatory Action Research	Flexible Time, Accessible Venue
Empowering Participant About Research without Influence	Non-Manipulative Questions- Validate by Participants (Flexible Time & Space)	Accessible in Multiple Formats & Availability of Lang Translators
No In-depth Interviews on Sensitive Topics; No Survey Forms	Dual Consent Approach- Participant to Researcher, Researcher to Participant (All Terms Approved by Participant)	Gender Neutral and Disability Friendly Facilities
Data Collection in Multiple Formats (No Video Recordings)	Gender and Disabled Friendly Interviewer	Availability of Supporting Staff
Unbiased Data Processing	Respecting Diverse Findings and Ensure Validation by Participant	No Storage of Unused Data
Acknowledgement/Co-Authorship	Final Draft Approval	Publish Accessible Findings with Anonymity as Open Access Data with Permission